

A NEED ANALYSIS FOR DESIGNING AN EDUPRENEURSHIP INTEGRATED TRANSLATION COURSE BOOK: STUDENTS AND LECTURERS PERSPECTIVES

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Abstract

Before creating a plan, developing, or even implementing, need analysis is the initial step in the process of designing teaching materials. We use qualitative research to analyze the data. As a result, lecturers said that translations' course-book was urgently needed since unavailability of course-book in the classroom. Moreover, lecturers consumed time and energy to compile the materials before teaching. In the other hand, students showed their weaknesses in grammar and vocabularies. Some topics also have been chosen to be studied. They had shared their willingness to be entrepreneur in translation field. So, integrating Edupreneurship in translation course-book is possible to create as a newly developed translation materials.

Keywords: Translation, Need Analysis, Students' And Lecturers' Perspective, Edupreneurship.

1. INTRODUCTION

Undergraduate students of English Literature Study Program, Fajar University, and Makassar, Indonesia are studying translation at the third and fourth semester as translation I and translation II. Students are proposed to be a translator after their graduation and demanded to be skilled in translating. To get students' readiness to work before their graduation, undergraduate English Literature Study Program should design curriculum to support one of their prospective works namely a translator during their studies.

Before designing syllabus, it is needed to observe the students' needs, weaknesses, strengths, willingness, and obstacles during studying translation from given questionnaires. Moreover, it would also need to review on lecturers inputs as a result of interviewing for syllabus matters, instructional materials, and any related comments towards currently problems in translation subject in the classroom. In Rosida et al., (2021), they used also students and lecturers to get the data to evaluate the institution and give future planning. Consequently, this research is conducted to do so.

To create graduates skilled in translating, syllabus and handbook should project the students as translator. Thus, it makes the researchers want to find out the current condition in the process of teaching and learning of translation. In contrary from preliminary observation, it was found that students do not have a hand book of translation to be studied in the classroom. Syllabus of translation does not show the systematic translation learning. Whereas, translation subject is

supposed to be effective and meet the learners' needs. A need analysis study is investigating important aspects of the course to which much needs is felt by the students (Aliakbari & Boghayeri, 2014). Therefore, this study aimed to examine the demands of students' needs and lecturers' perspectives as well as the process of teaching system and learning process realities of the field so as to come to a clear understanding of those drawbacks in translation class that currently exists in Undergraduate English Literature Study program at Fajar University, Makassar, Indonesia.

Considering the students are studying at Fajar University, as an entrepreneur university, it becomes additional insight for us to integrate the vision and mission of the institution into learning of translation. The agreement would be asked in the questionnaires for students and in the interviewing list for lecturers about their opinions in integrating the learning process of translation in the classroom towards Entrepreneurship in education (Edupreneurship).

Based on the explanation above, we propose these research questions below;

1. To what extend do the undergraduate students of English Literature Study Program Fajar University, Makassar, Indonesia need in studying translation?
2. And how is the lecturers' perspective during teaching translation at Undergraduate English Literature Study Program Fajar University, Makassar, Indonesia?

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

a. Previous Related Studies

Need analysis is the very beginning step to design a course book. The first process plays a crucial role in the design and development of any program of education. Need analysis has been done by many researchers. Sofyan, Sinar, & Tarigan (2020) studied about need analysis for online-based Translation as a Profession (TAP) course: a study at translation study program of University of Sumatera. They said that research on developing the course of TAP is required since the technology development greatly affect the learning system in their institution.

Siregar (2017) conducted the research on designing course as an initial approach to translation teaching since the translators found themselves lack in pedagogical knowledge. Experienced and skilled Translators believe that translation is learned by personal experiences and talents while teaching is a profession. Therefore, this article proposes the preliminary approach to teach translation for beginner and also attempts to suggest guideline how to design the translation course for beginners. The results show the course sequences of designing translation class for 7 meetings. From this research, it could be an alternative way for lecturers to conduct the translation subject.

b. Translation

Translation is as a processing of substituting a text in one language for a text in another (Catford, 1965; Ngozi, 2016). Translation is an operation performed on languages. It implies that translation cannot exist without language. Translation is not only about transferring of

words from one language to another, but it represents transformation of thoughts, feelings, and desires in one language into the same kind of thought, feelings, and desires of another language.

According to Quah (2006) that a translation theory may refer to many different things such as hypotheses, models, assumptions, beliefs, concepts and doctrines. It has numerous interpretations but only one aim: to increase the understanding of translation phenomena. Some general principles are proposed by Duff that supposed to be relevant to all translations (Duff, 1989), namely; translation should represent the original text meaning, the words orders and ideas should match the source language as closely as possible, translator must distinguish between formal or fixed expressions and personal expressions in which the writer or speaker sets the tone. And, translator should not change the style of the source language as much as possible. Other principles according to Duff are some idiomatic expressions are commonly hard to translate. To solve this problem, translator may keep the original word between inverted commas; keep the original expression with a literal explanation in brackets; use a close equivalent; and use a non-idiomatic or plain prose translation. The last principle is to sound the source text is more natural, it is a good way to set the text aside and translate a few sentences from memory in order to get the natural patterns of thought in the target language.

In the classroom of translation, students should understand about translation technique and methods. According to Molina and Albir (2002), technique is different from methods. Translation method justifies the entire translation text, while the translation technique focuses more on analyzing the components of language and classifying all the components so that an appropriate equivalent is found. Thus, Hartono states that translation is not only the category that can be used to analyzed translated texts, because there still other categories that can influence the analysis process in translation, such as coherence, cohesion, and thematic development (Hartono, 2020).

Referring to the terms of translation as a method, Molina and Albir argued that translation method is a way of carrying out translator's objective, for example, a global preference that affects the whole texts. In addition, Hartono said that translation method is more likely to be a way used by translators in translation process in accordance with the purpose or goal or aim of the translation (Hartono, 2020). It is like a global translator's option that affects the entire or whole text. So it greatly affects the translation results. It means that the translation results are largely determined by the translation method used by the translator because of the intention, purpose and aim that the translator tended, so it affects the results of the overall translation products. Apart from the differences of grouping translation into techniques while others classified them into techniques. Hartono (2020) states that Newmark (1988) classified literal translation and adaptation into methods while Molina and Albir (Molina & Albir, 2002) group both into techniques.

c. Need Analysis

Need analysis is the first step to the whole program planning process to create a course book. That is to say that need analysis plays crucial role in the design and development of any educational program (Shahri & Farimani, 2016). Sardi (1997) used need analysis to design a

syllabus to course design. Investigating need analysis is more complex than it may seem. Sardi adds that different people involved in the project of investigating need analysis may arrive at different conclusions depending on their views on language, learning and teaching. Therefore, need analysis is considered as an indispensable procedure in language teaching either for specific purposes or general.

According to Richard (1990) that need analysis has three functions in language curriculum design. They are:

1. It involves a large group of people such as learners, teachers, administrators and employers in the process planning
2. It serves to identify general or specific language needs so that they can be addressed while developing goals, objectives, and content for a language program.
3. It provides data that can serve as the basis for reviewing and evaluating an existing program.

d. Edupreneurship

Edupreneurship is a combination of the words education (education) and entrepreneurship (entrepreneurship). Edupreneurship wants to place entrepreneurial concepts and attitudes in the world of education. Education is often understood as a process of self-maturation combined with entrepreneur that means adventurer, risk taker, and entrepreneur. Entrepreneurs are more than just entrepreneurs because there must be more value and something different. Entrepreneurship as a complex bundle of skills (Eickhoff, 2008). Therefore, the skill of entrepreneurs is an ability to turn junk into gold through creativity and innovation in taking advantage of opportunities.

The application of edupreneurship is directed at forming the mental and entrepreneurial spirit of students in an effort to achieve success in the field of education. In the field of education, edupreneurship is about essentially taking what your ability and skill seize into commercial (Ihsan & Aulia, 2020). Edupreneurship is to transform learners' moves into a new venture, way of thinking and acting (Satterwhite, 2018). In short, Edupreneurship is not aimed at making students entrepreneurs, but rather at building edupreneur character in the field of education. This edupreneurship would be one of the graduate distinctions among others graduates.

3. METHOD

a. Overall Design of the Study

The method used in this study to find out the need analysis for designing an Edupreneurship integrated translation course book from students and lecturers perspectives is descriptive qualitative research. Need analysis is the first step from ADDIE (analyze, design, develop, implement, and evaluate) framework (Branch, 2009). It is used to develop instructional design model in translation class. Moreover, this study used a research and development design (Gall et al., 2003) to develop course materials of translation subject to be used by the students.

At the beginning of this research, analyze phase was conducted with the purpose of identifying, analyzing, and explaining the needs of students of English Literature Study Program at Fajar University, Makassar, Indonesia who were taking translation subject with regard to the real-world needs using the students' and lecturers' perceptions.

b. Participants

This research was conducted at English Literature Study Program, Faculty of Economics and Social sciences, Fajar University, Makassar, Indonesia. It is located in Prof. Abdurrahman Basalamah Street number 101 Makassar, South Sulawesi Indonesia. The sample of this research is the fourth semester students with the total sample is 20 students, and two of translation lecturers.

The number of students in this institution is lesser than other study program. But, it did not become an obstacle for researchers to investigate the condition of this institution. Therefore, his research applies the convenience sampling technique in taking the sample. The samples are the students who take translation course and the lecturer who is teaching translation.

c. Procedure

Before conducting the research, the researcher conducted the preliminary research by interviewing lecturers who teach translation to know the present condition in the program as well as to find the syllabus/material that presently used by the lecturer in the course.

Next, an open questionnaire was distributed to the students to know their need in learning translation. It took two weeks in collecting the answer from students since the researcher wants to take the response from students via online due social distance and pandemic of Covid-19. Therefore, the researcher sent the e-form based questionnaire to the students at English Literature Study Program.

Next, the researcher made an interview appointment with the lecturers. There were two translation lecturers that taught translation in different years. The interview conducted to know the lecturers' need regarding the condition of translation subject during their time to teach. There were four categories to sum lecturers' result of interviewing, such as; (a) interviewees' perceptions of the short comings of translation subject, (b) their perception of possible changes which can contribute to translation subject, (c) suggestions concerning the national curriculum and policies offered for the program, and (d) their perception of translation business.

d. Research instrument and data analyzed

The instruments used in this study were questionnaires and interviews. The questionnaires were distributed to the Undergraduates students of English Literature Study Program who have studied translation subject. Moreover, interviews were given to the lecturers who taught translation. To obtain data in this study, it uses qualitative research. The technique of qualitative data analysis used the flow by Miles & Huberman (1994) and employed NVivo.

4. RESULT

a. Students' questionnaires

To reveal the needs of undergraduate students in studying translation at English Literature Study Program Fajar University, Makassar, Indonesia, 20 undergraduate students were answered the distributed questionnaires from Google Form. The questionnaire was adapted from Hutchinson & Waters (Hutchinson & Waters, 1987) and Shahri & Farimani (2016) for interview.

At the beginning, it was asked about the students' skills and difficulties in English language skills. Self-assessment was asked to be more genuine about their abilities (Khizer et al., 2021). Students self-assessment is to helps students to learn, improve life skill, and motivates students (Andrews, 2016; Sharma et al., 2016). Students' score in academic report are less genuine due the other elements in scoring system were added, such as; attendance score, attitude score, tasks score, middle test score, and final test score Therefore, self-assessment is used to see the students' perspective on their abilities. The table is shown below:

Table 1: Students' self-assessment

Language Skills and Components	Very Weak	Weak	Fair	Good	Very Good	Total
Listening	0%	25%	40%	25%	10%	100%
Reading	0%	0%	45%	50%	5%	100%
Writing	0%	15%	60%	25%	0%	100%
Speaking	0%	35%	35%	25%	5%	100%
Grammar	0%	60%	25%	15%	0%	100%
Vocabulary	0%	25%	65%	10%	0%	100%
Bahasa Indonesia to English Translation	0%	20%	60%	20%	0%	100%
English to Bahasa Indonesia Translation	5%	35%	50%	10%	0%	100%
Average	0,6%	26,8%	47,5%	22,5%	2,5%	100%

Based on the result of students self-assessment, Table 1 proves that most of students' language skills at moderate level such as; vocabulary (65%), writing (60%), and 60% for grammar. Furthermore, it was found zero percent (0%) for students at very good level of language skills and translation; they had only 10% for listening and 5% for reading and speaking at very good level.

In translation, there were only one student at very weak for English to Bahasa Indonesia translation and zero percent for students' ability in translating Bahasa Indonesia to English. Moreover, 60% and 50% at fair level; 20% and 10% at good level. On the contrary, all students stated that they are not very good at doing translation.

Due the goal of this part is to find out students levelness on language skills relates to translation, this table concludes that the grammar skill in 60% at weak level becomes lecturers' obstacle to conduct translation class since grammar becomes one of the basic needs to build writing comprehensively. It is 47, 5% at fair level as the highest level. It means, students still do not have good enough abilities in English, and lecturers need to focus on the skills to be improved in teaching translation.

The results presented in Table 1 show students’ strengths and weaknesses in English language abilities. However, Figure 1 contains the topics/ sub-topics materials were asked for students on preferences studying translation. Since this research for beginner translator at fourth semester, they were offered their opinions on 6 learning topics. They considered the topics into a priority, important, or unimportant. The result shows the rank of each topic at Figure 1 below;

Figure 1: Topics of translation materials

According to respondents’ responses, it is ranked the topic of translation. The first of preferences students to learn is translation and common problems next is translation strategies, translation methods, translation and culture, translation and theories, and translation on abstract/ articles journal. Unfortunately, no students filled the blank option, but the summary of students’ answers was important for all of the topics.

Figure 2: Students’ preferences to study

This figure is to observe students’ preferences of study. The purpose of this questionnaires asked to the students was to design class activity in the process of teaching and learning. From four preferences, students preferred to study in a small group. It was 75% as the highest score. Then followed by self-study in 50%, students do not like to study alone. They prefer in pairs (50%) and put them in a big group (45%) rather than self-study. It could be said that translation subject was preferred to be studied in a small group rather than self—study.

Since the idea of this research is to integrate translation and entrepreneurship in education. Therefore, it was measured to see the importance of being students to be able to use translation skills in entrepreneurship, and how importance of translation syllabus or content was able to support the needs of students in entrepreneurship. Those questions were to measure students’

awareness on the relation of translation and entrepreneurship that translation might have potential in conducting service entrepreneur. The result was shown in Figure 3 below;

Figure 3: Translation and Entrepreneurship

From figure above, 40% of Students said that it is priority or very important for students to have an ability to use translation in entrepreneurship, and half of the students (50%) put it as an important decision. Similar to the next questionnaire, half of the students believed that it is important to create syllabus content should support students' need in doing entrepreneurship. Also, 35% answered it was a priority a researcher to design syllabus which is integrated with entrepreneurship.

To sum, students had shared their willingness to realize their wants of being entrepreneur in translation field. Translation and entrepreneurship are able to be implemented in one course of study namely translation subject. Researcher could project the syllabus and course book based on students' need to be an entrepreneur in providing translation service.

Related to entrepreneurship, this research was tabulated students characters as well, based on Takdir (2015) and Kemendikbud (2013) wrote entrepreneurial character. Those characters were asked to the students to identify their potential personality of being an entrepreneur. It is shown in Table 2 below;

Table 2: Students Entrepreneurial Characters

Entrepreneurial Characters	Very Weak	Weak	Fair	Good	Very Good	Total
Entrepreneurial skill	5%	45%	25%	20%	5%	100%
Have Leadership spirit	5%	20%	45%	30%	0%	100%
Communication skill	5%	15%	60%	15%	5%	100%
Have managerial skill	0%	30%	55%	15%	0%	100%
Be innovative	15%	20%	50%	10%	5%	100%
Have a persuasive skill	15%	20%	50%	10%	5%	100%
Have innovative behavior	5%	35%	50%	10%	0%	100%
Time management	15%	5%	60%	15%	5%	100%
Decision maker	0%	5%	60%	25%	10%	100%
Self-confidence	10%	20%	40%	20%	10%	100%
Be consistent	0%	0%	55%	40%	5%	100%
Average	6,8%	19,5%	50%	19,1%	4,5%	100%

From students' responses, Table 2 shows the diversity of characters owned by students. Some students are at moderate character namely; leadership spirit (45%), communication skill (60%), managerial skill (55%), be innovative (50%), persuasive skill (50%), Innovative behavior (50%), time management (60%), decision maker (60%), self-confidence (40%), and be consistent (55%). From 11 given questions, only entrepreneurship skill had low score, it is 25%. Unfortunately, most of students felt less at very good level of entrepreneurial characters.

Average score concludes that 4, 5% students at very good level and 5, 8% at very fair. In addition, at weak and good level had almost got the same score. They are 19, 5% and 19, 1%. Different from other level, half of students or 50% of participants were at fair level. It means, researcher would have no difficulty in compiling translation course-book since students have basic entrepreneurial characters. This would be an input in this research to develop translation subject that integrated Edupreneurship.

Validity and Reliability Test were done by using SPSS with a significance level of 5% and 20 respondents (students) obtained the value of $r_{table} = 0.432$. To obtain the validity if $r_{count} > r_{table}$ with a significance level of 5%, it can be stated that the instrument item is valid, and vice versa if $r_{count} < r_{table}$ with a significant level of 5% then the item is invalid. The result is shown below;

Table 3: Case Processing Summary

Case Processing Summary			
		N	%
Cases	Valid	20	100.0
	Excluded ^a	0	0.0
	Total	20	100.0
a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure			

From Table 3, it shows that the result of students' questionnaire was valid. From 44 questions with 20 samples, the result showed R_{table} is less than R_{count} . After doing validation test of questionnaire, it is followed by reliability test. Reliability shows the level of reliability if the instrument used is able to produce almost the same data at different times and places. The criterion for testing the reliability test is that if R_{count} is greater than R_{table} with a significance level of 5% (0.05), it can be stated that the measuring instrument is reliable, and conversely if R_{count} is smaller than R_{table} , the measuring instrument is not reliable. And the results of the reliability test can be seen in table 4;

Table 4: Reliability Test Result

Reliability Statistics			
R_{table}	Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items	Result
0.432	0.879	45	Reliable

From Table 4, it is concluded that the questionnaires given to the students was reliable because R_{count} is greater than R_{table} , 0.879 is greater than 0.432. Therefore, this research could go to the next step.

b. Semi-structured Interviews with Lecturers

The interviews have basically focused on general information, needs, difficulties and shortcomings perceived by lecturers. To do so, 10 general questions, verified by experts, were designed. The process of interviewing was done neatly with no problem. The first question was answered that there was a syllabus but both lecturers did not use it maximally to run their translation class. Lecturer A explains that the syllabus was not based on students' needs which he taught it was important part to design an appropriate material. In addition, lecturer B did small observation to what students needed and wanted that was to achieve process of teaching and learning maximally and effectively. Moreover, the second was asking about the provided syllabus and the reason of the lecturer to use it or not. The result showed that the two lecturers, they were hesitant to use syllabus. Due jumbled orders, undefined, not based on syllabus, and no longer relevant to the current condition in industries field which are more dynamic, unique, and complex. From that condition, it was concluded that translation syllabus was no longer suitable enough to be implemented in the classroom. Redesigning syllabus is important to overcome those problems which based on two lecturers.

The third is asking about a course-book or hand-book of translation that was provided by English Literature Study Program. And the two of lecturers claimed that there was not any specific course-book or hand-book in teaching translation. It was suggested to use several guidebooks but it was not compiled into one book and lecturer B assumed that the book is too theoretical and impractical. Moreover, lecturer A stated that he got confused and it consumed time in gathering some materials from different sources and articles journals. They hope from this research, lecturers could get more focus on teaching rather than busy on collecting some materials. The fourth question is about the importance of designing a course-book of translation. They said it is very important to design a course-book because with material or structured course book the proses of learning could be more focused and structured because the materials are already available and the achievements and targets to be achieved are also clear. This will help lecturers to teach more effectively and efficiently, and can also help students learn independently outside of the classroom with these teaching materials.

Next question is questioning about assessment of translation subject. The assessment was asked to see the way of translation lecturers to score the students' achievement. The two lecturers showed different way to evaluate the students since there was not any rubric to measure students' works. It could be assumed that translation assessment was subjectively done by lecturers. To see this problematic, this research would project also the rubric of translation assessment to evaluate students that ease lecturers to run the class. Moreover, the lecturers put big hope to this research to overcome the problems by designing a course-book, syllabus, and scoring system. A course-book should be based on students' abilities and ready to be used in any condition whether it is in online class or offline class. Besides giving input, lecturers complained on students' habit in doing tasks. Students used to use machine translator to finish their task. Moreover, lecturer B had a problem for students who translated less accurate. In addition, from lecturers' point of view on students' skill in translation class that students were in fair level of translation skill. Students were less in grammar, vocabularies, literally

translating, and short-cut translating by using machine translator. Those opinions might become one of researcher concern in designing a course-book to what students' skill should be enhanced. The last question was asked about lecturers' point of view about the ideas of researcher to find out a new way to teach students which based on the vision and mission of Fajar University which well known as an entrepreneur university. Lecturers said that this idea becomes positive answers and become one step stone to project students in the way of readiness to create a job, direct students to face work-world, and become added value as translator graduates.

5. DISCUSSION

This research presents findings that provide information about the efforts to improve the quality of the instructional process at English Literature Study Program Fajar University. Based on the findings above, the discussion can be summarized as follows:

A. The students' needs

This study explores students' needs in advance to design a course book of translation. Students' need is crucial as the feasibility of a product should be measured by the demands and needs of the users. Aliakbari & Boghayeri (2014) also performed need analysis to design ESP course. In measuring the needs of the students, the researcher tries to find out the presents condition of the students' capabilities in learning translation and their expectations. It includes the objectives in learning translation, how they think translation material should be delivered, and the endorsement of the four language skills within the course, the learning topics, their preferences, and their characters in entrepreneurship. A researcher could design any materials that meet the learning needs by the needs analysis. Need analysis has been done by some researchers on material development (Sardi, 1997; Shahri & Farimani, 2016; M. Siregar et al., 2018). They argued the needs of conducting needs analysis before designing any materials before designing any materials.

The questionnaire was given to 20 Undergraduate students of English Literature Study Program at Fajar University as a sample. From questionnaire in table 1, it was found the students levelness in four skills of English language. Students had 60% at weak level in mastering grammar while this becomes a problem for lecturer to run translation subject. Since every language has their own rule and system, it means grammatical system between source language and target language may result in translation changes (Oktari et al., 2019). Thus, grammar would be available in the project of designing translation book. Moreover, 47,5% is the average score at fair level. It was the highest score which means researcher would design a course book in intermediate level which focus on enhancing translation skill as compulsory goal and language skills as supportive skills, namely; grammar, writing, vocabularies, and other skills that considered as students' weaknesses. Besides identifying students' strengths and weaknesses on English language skills, we offered some topics to be preferred studied in translation subject. From responses in figure 1, students identified the topics into unimportant, less important, important, and priority. From 6 given topics, translation and common problems becomes the first rank then followed by translation strategies, next is translation methods, and

the forth is translation and culture, the fifth is translation and theories, and the last chosen topic is translation on abstract journal. Besides students chose the topics, we also gave a blank option to be filled by student, to what topic they would like to study. Unfortunately, no students filled the blank option. Noviyanti (2018) did the preference research also that aimed to improve students' reading motivation to study. It means listening to what students' wants to be studied made them motivated to improve their own skills (Mkonto, 2018). Next is the idea of the researcher to integrate the concept of edupreneurship in the learning of translation. Considering the students are studying at Fajar University which is well known as an entrepreneur university, we asked the students about their opinion towards syllabus of translation integrated to edupreneurship concept. Based on figure 2, students realized on the importance of utilize of translation ability in entrepreneur sector. And they also support in designing syllabus that support students' need in doing entrepreneurship in translation field. Higher education is supposed to be the factor of the development of socio-economic situation which means entrepreneurship in higher education is designed to empower staff and students to be enterprise, creative, and innovative (Melnikova & Zascerinska, 2016). It is not only in higher education, Kuat (2018) has implemented edupreneurship concept in vocational high school. It means the concept of entrepreneurship could be design in any field of education.

To see the potential aspect of students being an entrepreneur, we made students to assess themselves based on Takdir (2015) and Kemendikbud (2013) entrepreneurial characters. In table 2, average score data shows 50% or half of the students are at fair level which means it was not a bad score to combine two disciplines of knowledge become multi-disciplinary knowledge studied by students. Having both, translation and entrepreneurship, disciplinary knowledge may help to advance students' skill set and more adaptable to different contexts and environments as students are able to switch and think critically from one subject to another one. Moreover, students have improved their motivation based on class attendance and team teaching was positive and conducive to professional growth (Wicklein & Schell, 1995).

B. The lecturers' inputs

The interview results described the features of the existing translation material at English Literature Study Program, Fajar University. Significantly, the typical feature of translation subject is characterized by no handbook materials. The lecturers just collected the materials through the articles journal and books of translation from different sources. They were busy which consumes times to collect the materials since lecturers were seldom to use syllabus that provided by the study program. They felt that syllabus was no longer suitable enough to be implemented in the classroom. This situation was likely happen in Sofyan et al., (2020) to suggest to develop the course of translation since technology development greatly affect the learning system in their institution.

Moreover, the result of interviewing in domain of learning activities that covered assessment, learning activities, media, place and time allotment, it was found that the existing assessment was based on institution's rubric assessment, 10% for attendance, 10% for attitude, 40% for activities, 20% for middle test, and 20% for final test. But for the tests score, lecturers would not have fix scoring system. Furthermore, lecturers were complaining toward learning activities

of the students. Most of them used machine translator without doing revision which they did copy paste from the internet. Students used internet as media to do the task and had a lot of spare time in the classroom since they preferred to get silent rather than discuss toward their finished homework. There would be some possibilities; still do not understand since dependable on internet or the class is less interesting, less attractive, and less motivating. Thus, the researcher tries to develop the material and the activities by providing learning integration to Edupreneurship concept.

By giving motivation through learning activities, showing their prospective work after graduation and potential work as translator in any field of work through Edupreneurship integrated to translation subject would become interesting, interactive, and could direct the goal of learning. This idea has got positive feedback from respondents. They hope this becomes one step stone to project students in the way of readiness to create a job, direct students to face work-world, and become added value as translator graduates as well.

6. CONCLUSION

Based on the result of students' questionnaires, students' show their weaknesses on grammar and vocabularies, whereas those become one of basic needs to do translating. Some references topics, as students' willingness to study, also have been chosen to be studied and they preferred to study in a small group rather than self-study. In addition, students also had shared their willingness to realize their wants of being entrepreneur in translation field which should be implemented in the syllabus. It was also supported from students' responses that their entrepreneurial characters could be implemented in studying translation subject. From lecturers' interview, it is found that the current translation course was designed not based on students' needs and lecturers' experiences. Several topics on syllabus of translation subject are unsystematic which suggested modifying the course materials. Besides, this course is also needed to be integrated Edupreneurship as a newly developed translation materials and to get students ready to face work-world. Due translation business is still unfamiliar for students to earn. Therefore, renewal syllabus, design the scoring system, create a hand book or course book to run the class to ease the process of teaching and learning system are needed according to lecturers of translation at Fajar University. At the end, some suggestions could be given to other researchers to conduct the research. Other researcher could add respondents like stake holders, graduates, or translation institution that giving additional insight in designing syllabus and course book for English Literature students.

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